

1 **Supplementary Materials**

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Figure S1. Changes in (a) temperature and (b) relative humidity during storage under different conditions. Storage in GrainPro® bag and controlled atmosphere chamber (blue line), storage in polyethylene bag and ambient conditions on a laboratory bench (red line).

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3 **Figure S2. Color imaging system used in the experiment. Device: Nikon D5200; lens: 40 mm f/2.8 G; focal**
4 **length: 40 mm; focus mode: AF-S; aperture: f/16; shutter speed: 1/15 sec; exposure comp.: +1.7 EV; ISO**
5 **sensitivity: ISO 1000; color space: sRGB; and filter: Nisi DW1 Wide Band Super Pro MC UV filter 52 mm.**
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4 **Figure S3. Uniformity of radicle emergence of indica rice seeds after scoring using different methods, where**
5 **red is visual analysis and blue is SVRice software. Linear regression lines are shown.**

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3 **Figure S4. The relationship of each rice seed vigor parameter. The distribution of each parameter is shown**
 4 **on the diagonal. The bivariate scatter plots with a fitted line are displayed on the bottom of the diagonal.**
 5 **The values of the correlation and the significance level as stars are indicated on the top of the diagonal. A**
 6 **symbol, ***, is assigned to significance level at $p \leq 0.001$. Maximum radicle emergence (MaxRE), radicle**
 7 **emergence speed (t_{50}), uniformity of radicle emergence (U_{7525}), area under the curve of the radicle**
 8 **emergence fitted curve (AUC) and mean radicle emergence times (MRET) of the radicle emergence fitted**
 9 **curve are displayed as well as the saturated salt accelerated aging (SSAA) test.**

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Table S1. Outputs of k-means cluster analysis of 40 rice seed samples used in the experiment^[a].

Code	Storage time (months)	Storage condition	Maximum radicle emergence (%)	Radicle emergence speed (hours)	Uniformity of radicle emergence (hours)	Area under the curve of the radicle emergence fitted curve	Mean radicle emergence time (hours)	K-mean (K=2)	K-mean (K=3)
A	0	Controlled	98.5	75.1	28.5	209.3	78.8	1	1
B	0	Controlled	80.8	184.3	107.5	86.0	164.0	2	2
C	0	Controlled	95.8	80.5	22.9	194.7	82.8	1	1
D	0	Controlled	92.3	76.8	31.1	192.3	81.1	1	1
E	0	Controlled	91.3	78.1	27.9	193.0	81.5	1	1
F	0	Controlled	95.3	57.4	20.7	218.3	60.1	1	1
G	0	Controlled	91.0	90.2	83.7	171.7	97.8	1	3
H	0	Controlled	93.8	68.9	21.7	201.1	71.3	1	1
A	6	Controlled	100.0	64.1	25.0	229.7	67.5	1	1
B	6	Controlled	100.0	76.1	36.5	215.5	81.9	1	1
C	6	Controlled	99.8	69.9	28.3	223.9	73.8	1	1
D	6	Controlled	100.0	66.6	32.1	227.5	71.8	1	1
E	6	Controlled	96.0	73.2	31.7	212.1	77.9	1	1
F	6	Controlled	100.0	49.5	22.3	245.3	53.1	1	1
G	6	Controlled	98.3	80.0	58.2	202.2	89.6	1	1
H	6	Controlled	98.5	59.6	34.4	217.1	65.6	1	1
A	6	Ambient	97.3	114.8	56.9	167.6	120.6	1	3
B	6	Ambient	92.3	144.7	103.4	129.1	138.2	2	3
C	6	Ambient	99.5	83.4	25.0	210.6	86.0	1	1
D	6	Ambient	99.5	72.3	33.2	221.1	77.5	1	1
E	6	Ambient	98.0	104.0	53.4	181.2	110.9	1	3
F	6	Ambient	99.0	54.5	18.0	238.4	56.8	1	1
G	6	Ambient	48.3	219.3	155.6	42.3	154.7	2	2
H	6	Ambient	98.8	80.5	49.0	203.7	88.5	1	1
A	12	Controlled	98.0	74.9	16.6	206.6	76.3	1	1
B	12	Controlled	97.0	88.4	53.4	191.9	96.6	1	1
C	12	Controlled	99.3	79.4	34.3	208.2	84.3	1	1
D	12	Controlled	99.5	77.1	36.7	208.5	82.9	1	1
E	12	Controlled	95.5	78.2	30.9	195.8	82.4	1	1
F	12	Controlled	100.0	61.0	22.1	230.2	63.9	1	1
G	12	Controlled	94.3	102.2	65.6	166.6	109.9	1	3
H	12	Controlled	100.0	77.7	54.7	202.7	85.1	1	1
A	12	Ambient	72.3	203.8	108.3	66.0	173.7	2	2
B	12	Ambient	48.0	195.9	105.3	48.5	170.4	2	2
C	12	Ambient	98.8	112.0	48.9	177.2	117.8	1	3
D	12	Ambient	98.8	89.2	44.4	200.3	95.8	1	1
E	12	Ambient	75.0	198.4	97.8	72.8	178.0	2	2
F	12	Ambient	98.8	71.5	34.6	217.7	77.0	1	1
G	12	Ambient	4.5	214.4	113.6	4.3	171.5	2	2
H	12	Ambient	93.5	133.4	96.6	143.1	129.8	2	3

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^[a] Values represent the arithmetic mean of radicle emergence indices from the SVRice package after storage for 0, 6 and 12 months under controlled and ambient conditions.

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